

Merge-and-Shrink for SSPs with Prune Transformations — Proof Appendix

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Abstract

This proof appendix contains the sketched or omitted proofs of the ECAI 2024 paper “Merge-and-Shrink for SSPs with Pruning Transformations” by Klößner et al. The notation follows the original paper.

For the proofs below, recall again the definition of the transformed policy $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)$ as given in the paper:

Definition 6. Let $\langle \Theta, \Theta', \sigma, \lambda \rangle$ be a transformation, let π be a policy for Θ and let $s \in S_\Theta$ be some starting state. The transformed policy $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)$ of π for s is defined by

$$tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)(p')(\mathfrak{T}') := \frac{\sum_{p \in tpath_\tau^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^\pi[Cyl(p)] \cdot \sum_{\mathfrak{T} \in ttr_\tau^{-1}(\mathfrak{T}')} \pi(p)(\mathfrak{T})}{\sum_{p \in tpath_\tau^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^\pi[Cyl(p)]}$$

if $\Pr_s^\pi[\bigcup_{p \in tpath_\tau^{-1}(p')} Cyl(p)] > 0$, and $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)(p')(\mathfrak{T}') := 0$ otherwise.

In the paper, the following theorem was stated without being formally shown. We will prove it in the following.

Theorem 2. Let $\tau = \langle \Theta, \Theta', \sigma, \lambda \rangle \in \mathbf{CONS}_{L+T}$ and let $s \in S_\Theta$. For all policies π with $Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s) \subseteq dom(\sigma)$ and every set of target states $T \subseteq S_\Theta$:

- a) $Reach_{\Theta, tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)}^\rightarrow(\sigma(s)) = \sigma(Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s))$ and
- b) If $\pi \in Sols_\Theta(s, T)$, then $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi) \in Sols_{\Theta'}(\sigma(s), \sigma(T))$.

To show this theorem, we first start with two lemmata. In the following, let $Prefs_\pi(s) := \{p \mid \Pr_s^\pi[Cyl(p)] > 0\}$ be the set of execution prefixes that can possibly be generated by a policy π with starting state s . Loosely speaking, the first lemma states that under the assumption \mathbf{CONS}_L and \mathbf{CONS}_T , as well as the assumption that every reachable state of the policy π with starting state s is kept by the transformation ($Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s) \subseteq dom(\sigma)$), every intermediate path p that can potentially be generated by π can be mapped to a transformed path $tpath_\tau(p)$ that exists within the transformed transition system Θ' . Additionally, if the original path reached a set of target states T , then the transformed path reaches the corresponding set of target states $\sigma(T)$.

Lemma 1. Let $\tau = \langle \Theta, \Theta', \sigma, \lambda \rangle$ be a transformation, let π be a policy, let $s \in S_\Theta$ be a starting state and let $p \in FPaths(\Theta)$.

- a) If $\tau \in \mathbf{CONS}_{L+T}$, $Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s) \subseteq dom(\sigma)$ and $p \in Prefs_\pi(s)$, then $p \in dom(tpath_\tau)$ and $tpath_\tau(p) \in FPaths(\Theta')$.
- b) Let $T \subseteq S_\Theta$ be a set of target states. If the assumptions of Lemma 1a) hold and additionally $p \in Finish_\Theta(T)$, then $tpath_\tau(p) \in Finish_{\Theta'}(\sigma(T))$.

Proof. Let $p = s_0 \mathfrak{T}_0 \dots s_n$ in the following.

We consider Lemma 1a) first. First of all, we have $s_0, \dots, s_n \in Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s)$ and also $supp(\mathfrak{T}_i) \subseteq Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s)$ for $0 \leq i < n$. Since $Reach_{\Theta,\pi}^\rightarrow(s) \subseteq dom(\sigma)$ by assumption and $\tau \in \mathbf{CONS}_L$, we conclude that $s_0, \dots, s_n \in dom(\sigma)$ and $\mathfrak{T}_0, \dots, \mathfrak{T}_{n-1} \in dom(ttr_\tau)$. In particular, p is transformable, i.e., $p \in dom(tpath_\tau)$. Moreover, because of $\tau \in \mathbf{CONS}_T$, we also have $ttr_\tau(\mathfrak{T}_0), \dots, ttr_\tau(\mathfrak{T}_{n-1}) \in T_{\Theta'}$ and therefore $tpath_\tau(p) \in FPaths(\Theta')$.

For Lemma 1b), we additionally have $p \in Finish_\Theta(T)$ so we have $s_n \in T$. As noted above, $s_n \in dom(\sigma)$, so we conclude $\sigma(s_n) \in \sigma(T)$ and $p \in Finish_{\Theta'}(\sigma(T))$ in particular. \square

Next, we prove that, under the same assumptions as stated earlier, there is a nice relationship between the probability measures of the original policy with starting state s and the transformed policy with starting state $\sigma(s)$. Namely, the probability that the transformed policy generates an intermediate transformed path p' is equal to the probability that π generates some corresponding intermediate concrete path $p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')$. The same also holds for the final path generated upon termination.

Lemma 2. *Let $\tau = \langle \Theta, \Theta', \sigma, \lambda \rangle$ be a transformation, let π be a policy and let $s \in S_{\Theta}$ be a starting state. Moreover, let $p' \in FPath_s(\Theta')$ be a path of Θ' . If $\tau \in \mathbf{CONS}_{L+R}$ and $Reach_{\Theta, \pi}(s) \subseteq dom(\sigma)$, then:*

$$\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)}[Cyl(p')] = \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \quad (1)$$

$$\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)}[p'] = \Pr_s^{\pi}[tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')] \quad (2)$$

Proof. Let $p' = s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_n$ in the following.

Proof of Equation (1) First, we show Equation (1). By definition of the probability measure, we have

$$\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)}[Cyl(p')] = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)(\mathfrak{X}'_i) \cdot \delta_{\mathfrak{X}'_i}(s'_{i+1}).$$

If $\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] = 0$ for some prefix $s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i$ of p' , then for the right hand side of Equation (1) we have $\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \leq \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] = 0$ and the right hand side must be zero. The equation above has a factor $tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i) = 0$ in this case by definition of $tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)$, thus the left hand side also evaluates to zero. All in all, both sides are zero under this assumption and the claim is shown.

Now assume $\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] > 0$. We apply the definition of $tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)$ and obtain:

$$\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau, s}(\pi)}[Cyl(p')] = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \cdot \sum_{\mathfrak{X} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i)} \pi(p)(\mathfrak{X}) \cdot \delta_{\mathfrak{X}'_i}(s'_{i+1})}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

In the next step, we exploit that $\mathfrak{X} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i)$ in the sum, from which it follows that $\delta_{\mathfrak{X}'_i} = lift[\sigma](\delta_{\mathfrak{X}})$.

$$\dots = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \cdot \sum_{\mathfrak{X} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i)} \pi(p)(\mathfrak{X}) \cdot lift[\sigma](\delta_{\mathfrak{X}})(s'_{i+1})}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

We now apply the definition of $lift[\sigma]$, leading to:

$$\dots = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \cdot \sum_{\mathfrak{X} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i)} \pi(p)(\mathfrak{X}) \cdot \sum_{s \in \sigma^{-1}(s'_{i+1})} \delta_{\mathfrak{X}}(s)}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

$$\dots = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{\langle p, \mathfrak{X}, s \rangle \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i) \times ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i) \times \sigma^{-1}(s'_{i+1})} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \cdot \pi(p)(\mathfrak{X}) \cdot \delta_{\mathfrak{X}}(s)}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

Finally, we make use of the fact $\Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] \cdot \pi(p)(\mathfrak{X}) \cdot \delta_{\mathfrak{X}}(s) = \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p\mathfrak{X}s)]$ and simplify:

$$\dots = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{\langle p, \mathfrak{X}, s \rangle \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i) \times ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{X}'_i) \times \sigma^{-1}(s'_{i+1})} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p\mathfrak{X}s)]}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

$$\dots = [s'_0 = s'] \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i \mathfrak{X}'_i s'_{i+1})} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}{\sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(s'_0 \mathfrak{X}'_0 \dots s'_i)} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]}$$

This is a telescoping product, in which every numerator cancels with the following denominator, and only the final numerator for $i = n - 1$ remains. Note in particular that $[s'_0 = s'] = \Pr_s^{\pi}[\bigcup_{s_0 \in \sigma^{-1}(s'_0)} Cyl(s_0)]$. Therefore:

$$\dots = \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)]$$

This concludes the proof of Equation (1).

Proof of Equation (2) To prove Equation (2), we first express the event $\{p'\}$ as the event of all executions with prefix p' , without those which continue along some transition to some state. Then we simplify the equations using our assumptions and Equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)}[p'] &= \Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)} [Cyl(p') \setminus (\bigcup_{\mathfrak{T}' \in T_{\Theta'}} \bigcup_{t' \in S_{\Theta'}} Cyl(p'\mathfrak{T}'t'))] \\
&= \Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)} [Cyl(p')] - \sum_{\mathfrak{T}' \in T_{\Theta'}} \sum_{t' \in S_{\Theta'}} \Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)} [Cyl(p'\mathfrak{T}'t')] \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] - \sum_{\mathfrak{T}' \in T_{\Theta'}} \sum_{t' \in S_{\Theta'}} \sum_{\substack{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p') \\ \mathfrak{T} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(\mathfrak{T}') \\ t \in \sigma^{-1}(t')}} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p\mathfrak{T}t)] \quad (\text{by Equation (1)}) \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} (\Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] - \sum_{\mathfrak{T} \in ttr_{\tau}^{-1}(T_{\Theta'})} \sum_{t \in \sigma^{-1}(S_{\Theta'})} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p\mathfrak{T}t)]) \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} (\Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] - \sum_{\mathfrak{T} \in T_{\Theta}} \sum_{t \in S_{\Theta}} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p\mathfrak{T}t)]) \quad (\text{by Lemma 1a}) \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} (\Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] - \Pr_s^{\pi} [\bigcup_{\mathfrak{T} \in T_{\Theta}} \bigcup_{t \in S_{\Theta}} Cyl(p\mathfrak{T}t)]) \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p) \setminus (\bigcup_{\mathfrak{T} \in T_{\Theta}} \bigcup_{t \in S_{\Theta}} Cyl(p\mathfrak{T}t))] \\
&= \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')} \Pr_s^{\pi} [p] \\
&= \Pr_s^{\pi} [tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')]
\end{aligned}$$

This shows the claim. \square

We now use both of these lemmata to prove the initial claim.

Theorem 2. Let $\tau = \langle \Theta, \Theta', \sigma, \lambda \rangle \in \text{CONSL}_{\text{L+T}}$ and let $s \in S_{\Theta}$. For all policies π with $\text{Reach}_{\Theta, \pi}^{\rightarrow}(s) \subseteq \text{dom}(\sigma)$ and every set of target states $T \subseteq S_{\Theta}$:

- a) $\text{Reach}_{\Theta, tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)}^{\rightarrow}(\sigma(s)) = \sigma(\text{Reach}_{\Theta, \pi}^{\rightarrow}(s))$ and
- b) If $\pi \in \text{Sols}_{\Theta}(s, T)$, then $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi) \in \text{Sols}_{\Theta'}(\sigma(s), \sigma(T))$.

Proof. The inclusion from left to right holds without any assumptions, since $\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)}[Cyl(p')] > 0$ for some path $p' \in \text{FPaths}(\Theta')$ implies that there is a concrete path $p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(p')$ with $\Pr_s^{\pi}[Cyl(p)] > 0$ by Equation (1), where we have $\text{last}(p) \in \text{dom}(\sigma)$ and $\text{last}(p') = \sigma(\text{last}(p))$ in particular.

For the other direction, acknowledge that for every path $p \in \text{Prefs}_{\pi}(s)$, we have $p \in \text{dom}(tpath_{\tau})$ and $tpath_{\tau}(p) \in \text{FPaths}(\Theta')$ by Lemma 1a) in the context of our assumptions. Therefore,

$$0 < \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] \leq \sum_{p \in tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(tpath_{\tau}(p))} \Pr_s^{\pi} [Cyl(p)] = \Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)} [Cyl(tpath_{\tau}(p))]$$

where the last equality follows from Equation (1) and $\sigma(\text{last}(p)) = \text{last}(tpath_{\tau}(p))$ in particular.

For Theorem 2b), we use Equation (2), followed by Lemma 1b). In particular, from Lemma 1b) we obtain the fact that $tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(\text{Finish}_{\Theta'}(\sigma(T))) \supseteq \text{Finish}_{\Theta}(T) \cap \text{Prefs}_{\pi}(s)$ in the context of our assumptions. Hence:

$$\Pr_{\sigma(s)}^{tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi)} [\text{Finish}_{\Theta'}(\sigma(T))] = \Pr_s^{\pi} [tpath_{\tau}^{-1}(\text{Finish}_{\Theta'}(\sigma(T)))] \geq \Pr_s^{\pi} [\text{Finish}_{\Theta}(T) \cap \text{Prefs}_{\pi}(s)] = 1.$$

Thus, $tpol_{\tau,s}(\pi) \in \text{Sols}_{\Theta'}(\sigma(s), \sigma(T))$. \square